

Laying the Foundations for Ethical Reviews at Statistics Canada

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Abstract

Ethical questions emerge as National Statistical Organizations (NSOs) adopt new practices, methods and analytical tools to produce better quality information. These questions need to be addressed with the help of a non-arbitrary approach that can enable a culture of trust between NSOs and the individuals or businesses on which they gather data. To find such an approach, Statistics Canada reviewed a variety of guidelines. They were typically found to be either too narrow or too wide in scope to address the issues that are currently being discussed within the organization. Moreover, many guidelines seemed to be focused on individual responsibilities and much less on the situations where these responsibilities can fail. This is a gap that needs to be addressed and this paper shows how Statistics Canada is taking on this task. As a result, Statistics Canada is likely to contribute to this variety of existing guidelines as different organizations may face unique situations where ethical questions may surface.

Key Words: data ethics, guidelines, national statistical organizations, situationism, trust

1. Introduction

For many years now, there has been a steady expansion in terms of the nature of the data that is acquired; the methods used to acquire and analyze the data; and the variety of services that Statistics Canada provides (Arora 2018). Such an expansion can be attributed to four main causes: 1- a need for more granular, complete, and timely data, 2- declining response rates of traditional survey methods, 3- the prohibitive costs of surveys, and 4- technological developments and expertise. This expansion is causing a paradigm shift¹ that not only raises methodological questions, but it also raises several ethical challenges about the appropriate use of data that need to be addressed formally.

These challenges need to be addressed with the help of a non-arbitrary approach that can enable a culture of trust between NSOs and the individuals or businesses on which they gather data. To find such an approach, Statistics Canada reviewed a variety of guidelines. They were typically found to be either too narrow or too wide in scope to address the issues that are currently being discussed within the organization. Moreover, many guidelines seemed to be focused on individual responsibilities and much less on the situations where those responsibilities can fail. This is a gap that needs to be addressed and this paper shows how Statistics Canada is taking on this task. As a result, Statistics Canada is likely to contribute to this variety of existing guidelines as different organizations may face unique situations where ethical questions may surface.

This paper contains two main sections. In the first, examples of ethical questions and risks are given as the driving factor for a systematic approach to ethics within a NSO like Statistics Canada. In the

¹ The expression "paradigmatic shift" is used to mean that the standard set of problems and solutions used by a group of scientists are being replaced by a new one. It is very close (if not identical) to some interpretations of the Kuhnian notions of "shift in paradigm" (Bird 2018).

second, lessons learned from consulting different ethical guidelines are given and a description of how they have been taken into account is provided.

2. The Need for a Systematic Approach to Ethical Questions Related to the Appropriate Use of Data

With the advantage of hindsight, the ethical challenges that NSOs are facing have not always been described in the most comprehensive terms. In 2005, William Seltzer categorized the main ethical challenges that arise in official statistics under three categories:

- a) Use of sound methodology
- b) Protection of confidentiality
- c) Integrity of the statistical agencies and the national statistical system (i.e., free of political influence)

Categories a) and c) cover ethically relevant dimensions that go beyond legal and confidentiality concerns. However, as NSOs acquire more administrative data than before; as they provide a wider variety of custom services and as they produce and manipulate more disaggregated data on specific segments of society, they now face challenges that fall well beyond this classification.

Here are six examples of activities and situations that have been identified, discussed, and/or addressed at Statistics Canada before they could become problematic:

- Bypassing the explicit refusal of a community to participate in our surveys by acquiring administrative data, thus undermining current and future efforts to engage with that community.
- Imputing personal information based on sensitive sociodemographic variables. This can propagate harmful stereotypes.
- Asking personal and sensitive information by proxy. For example, asking about gender by proxy could be perceived as being too intrusive, especially if the proxy is not a close family member. Privacy intrusions can undermine the trust of potential respondents, and the quality of the information can be compromised.
- Providing our expertise or analytical products to inform the private sector. This kind of activity can potentially undermine our credibility as an impartial source of information for all Canadians.
- Providing our expertise or algorithms to external partners to automate administrative decisions on individuals. This can conflict with our promise to use data for statistical purposes only and undermine the trust of our respondents.
- Providing indexes (e.g., for health or crime vulnerability) to help allocate resources. This can lead to reputational risks if computed with machine learning algorithms that are difficult to interpret.

Each example demonstrates the existence of specific risks for a NSO that are not legal risks, prompting the following questions: “It is legal, but it is ethical?” or “It can be done, but should it be done?”. Faced with such examples, Statistics Canada needed an approach to rigorously identify, discuss and address situations that raises these questions. In order to find such an approach, several ethical guidelines have been reviewed. The next section discusses the results of those reviews.

3. Lessons learned from Consulting Various Ethical Guidelines

The examination of available ethical guidelines (including guidance and frameworks)² showed how their scope was not perfectly aligned with the situations that Statistics Canada is currently facing in terms of data ethics (see the previous section). Perhaps this should not come as a surprise given the specificity of Statistics Canada’s activities. What is interesting however is the focus of some guidelines, such as the ASA, on responsibilities:

² See (Tractenberg & Park, 2023) for examples of such documents.

- Responsibilities to Stakeholders
- Responsibilities to Research Subjects, Data Subjects, or Those Directly Affected by Statistical Practices
- Responsibilities to Members of Multidisciplinary Teams
- Responsibilities to Fellow Statistical Practitioners and the Profession
- Responsibilities of Leaders, Supervisors, and Mentors in Statistical Practice
- Responsibilities Regarding Potential Misconduct

Responsibilities are important and the ASA Ethical Guidelines for Statistical Practices contains a very comprehensive list. From Statistics Canada’s perspective, what seems to be missing from this kind of document is a focus on situations where those responsibilities can fail. Such a focus can be found in the literature of situationism in ethics. In this section, it will be shown how Statistics Canada implemented some lessons from situationism in its approach to data ethics.

3.1 Implementing Lessons from Situationism

Situationism focuses on the thesis that individuals seem to underestimate or be completely unaware of the situational factors that can lead them to making desirable or undesirable actions and to overestimate the importance of their own character. It is a thesis that appears to be substantiated by a plethora of experimental results such as this one:

“If you are standing outside a bakery with the smell of fresh bread in the air, one study showed, you are more likely to help a stranger than if you are standing outside a “neutral-smelling dry goods store”” (Bloom, 2008).

This is interesting from an ethical perspective because it shows an apparent failure on behalf of most participants to these experiments to be appropriately sensitive to the morally relevant considerations (Miller 2023). A compassionate person should not be sensitive in this way to the smell of fresh bread. They should help a stranger because it is the right thing to do. We are expecting moral agents to act rationally or virtuously and not because of environmental factors that can go unnoticed.

NSOs could certainly spread the smell of fresh bread in their offices, but this is not the main lesson that should be taken away from these experiments. What would be more important is to identify the conditions under which ethical risks are likely to occur and aim at avoiding them altogether. This is actually the kind of moral advice that situationists have in mind:

“If you are trying not to give into temptation [...], to smoke [...], the best advice is not to try to develop “will-power” or “self-control”. Instead, [...] Do not carry cigarettes or a lighter and avoid people who smoke!” (Harman 2003, 91)

Similarly, if NSOs do not want to bypass the explicit refusal to participate in surveys in order to keep a relationship of trust; do not want to ask a sensitive question via an inappropriate proxy; or do not want to jeopardize their (real and perceived) neutrality from political parties and private enterprises; then the best advice is not to try to develop the ‘will-power’ or the ‘self-control’ of their employees. Instead, put in place some governance that will make it very difficult, if not impossible, for those risks to materialize in the first place.

Looking at the ethical questions and risks facing Statistics Canada, we find that they are not the result of a change in the moral character of its employees, but the result of new practices embedded into pre-existing ones. This creates situations that have ethical implications. This is why situationism provides valuable insights.

It is in that spirit that the Data Ethics Secretariat at Statistics Canada laid the foundations for their ethical reviews under six guiding principles instead of a list of responsibilities or duties. Here are the principles:

- Benefits to Canadians
- Transparency and Accountability
- Quality
- Trust and Sustainability
- Privacy and Security
- Fairness and Do no harm

These principles essentially function as labels for six distinct clusters of questions, considerations and recommendations that are discussed and documented as cases are being reviewed by internal experts on various topics (e.g. ethics, statistics, machine learning, conflict of interest, privacy, health, sociology, economics, etc...). Situationism is infused in those reviews because these clusters are adapted to well-known situations where ethical risks are likely to occur. They are not designed to focus on individuals failing to uphold their responsibilities. They are focused on situational factors that can undermine our responsibilities as emerging practices interact and sometimes clash with pre-existing ones.

3.1.1 Example: Administrative Data Acquisition

For example, the acquisition of personal administrative data is an activity that is becoming more prevalent within NSOs. Such acquisitions are usually done without the explicit consent of the individuals and those same individuals can be unaware of such acquisition altogether. Under these conditions, the expected benefits of this data for individuals and communities can be misunderstood and privacy intrusions can become a concern. This raises the likelihood of acquiring information from individuals and communities that might not trust a NSO with their data, let alone understand why that NSO needs this data. All these factors are considered when conducting a review under the six guiding principles.

The advice given from such reviews also has a situationist flavor. It is not focused on ‘will-power’ or ‘self-control’ to uphold the values underlying the six guiding principles. The advice is focused on eliminating situational factors in favor of new ones such that we can enhance the transparency and reasoning behind every administrative data acquisition by design. For example, Statistics Canada lists all the administrative data coming from non-public sources and microdata linkages on its website: [Statistics Canada's Trust Centre \(statcan.gc.ca\)](https://www25.statcan.gc.ca/nor/university/trust/). Every administrative data acquisition also goes through an ethical review that requires documenting the expected benefits of such an acquisition and an initial assessment of the quality of the data to ensure that those benefits are credible. Such reviews also consider both the level of privacy intrusion involved in the acquisition and how teams aim at minimizing the intrusion.

The advice also underscores the importance of improving the communication between different groups within the organization to ensure that their respective activities are not incoherent with another. For example, one group might have the task of estimating the total population of Canadian provinces and the other, of improving relationships with Indigenous communities. The work of one group may impact the other and ethical risks can arise when there is a lack of communication. These communications are not left to the ‘good-will’ of the teams but imposed by design during planned and recurrent meetings such as the Data Ethics Committee meetings. This is how the expression ‘ethical by design’ becomes meaningful.

3.1.2 Example: New Survey Questionnaires

Another example where our responsibilities can fail under specific situational factors occurs when there is an increase in the collection of disaggregated socio-demographic information such as gender (a new practice) and when that need is met with pre-existing survey questionnaires that ask such questions by proxy (an older practice). This raises the risk of using an inappropriate proxy, like a neighbour or an accountant (in business surveys).

These concerns are typically addressed through a mandatory review process where new questionnaires are reviewed with the help of a form that specifically identifies questions that are

asked by proxy and the characteristics of the proxy (e.g., family member, legal guardian, neighbour, accountant, etc...). As we can see, the cluster of questions, considerations and recommendations under the label ‘privacy and security’ will be very different in this case in comparison with the previous example under 3.1.1. However, the underlying motivation is the same. It is to be able to identify situations that can raise ethical concerns and to implement changes in our workflow in order to minimize risks.

3.1.3 Example: The Use of New Algorithms to Facilitate Decision Making

A third example where our responsibilities can fail under specific situational factors arises when there is a greater appetite in using new algorithms to meet the information needs of a client. The growing knowledge in machine learning allows to better account for non-linear relationships between variables of interest. NSOs like Statistics Canada encourage the growing use and expertise in that domain. Yet, this appetite for innovation can sometimes be mis adapted for clients who need to be able to justify and explain the decisions they make based on the information produced by those algorithms. Some of them are rather difficult to interpret.

For instance, let us consider the computation of a health vulnerability score for specific geographical regions. Let us also assume that this score will help determine if a region can obtain more resources than another for health-related initiatives. If a community within a certain geography wants to understand why they are receiving fewer resources for health-related initiatives than another, then someone needs to be able to explain and justify discrepancies in health vulnerability scores. Failure to do so can pose a reputational risk for the NSO responsible for producing the scores. This kind of risk is currently assessed, through questionnaires that are supporting mandatory ethical reviews of administrative data acquisitions within the organization. They fall under the “Transparency and Accountability” principle.

4. Conclusion

Statistics Canada, like other NSOs, face ethical questions as they acquire, manipulate, analyse and share data. It is important to address those questions in a rigorous way. In order to work towards that goal Statistics Canada reviewed several existing ethical guidelines or other types of documents on data ethics. Some of them are listed in (Tractenberg & Park, 2023). Unsurprisingly, such guidelines are not tailored to the specific challenges that Statistics Canada encounters, but more importantly, some of them solely focus on the importance of responsibilities. Responsibilities are very important, and this paper does not argue that this is a mistaken way to approach data ethics. However, this focus on responsibilities generates the following question: how can such responsibilities fail?

It has been argued that situationism can provide valuable insight in that respect. Most ethical discussions that are currently taking place are not the result of a change in moral character of the employees of Statistics Canada. They are usually the result of unintended consequences of new practices. Within NSOs, responsibilities can fail when innovative trends are embedded in pre-existing practices. As a result, Statistics Canada opted for an approach that aims at identifying and addressing those situations. The organization does so with the help of six guiding principles that are operationalized according to the specificity of those situations. The principles have been found to be useful for identifying and mitigating risks. After all, principles are impactful when they help with addressing specific challenges, preventing risks, and improving the work of an organization.

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